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Evaluation & Impact Assessment
SATISFACTION SURVEY

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>ENGAGING & INCENTIVISING INTERROGATING CREATING ADDRESSING APPLYING</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>Useful during all stages of the initiative and iteratively throughout the project.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Any size. If the number of actors involved in the survey is high the tools would be more useful.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>No technical skills required.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>Depends on the amount of actors involved in the survey.</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>Access to a computer, tablet or phone that has the MS Office package installed.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tools #2.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Image source: [Roman Synkevych on Unsplash](#)

Purpose

The tool is useful to determine simply the level of satisfaction of the actors who belong to an initiative. In addition, it allows the visual and intuitive analysis of the answers for future decision-making.

Background and Logic

For innovation initiatives that carry out an interactive process, it is essential to establish and maintain relationships with different types of actors. A good connection between the parties facilitates the exchange of knowledge and, consequently, the possibility of creating the desired interaction. The actors can be internal or external to the initiative and are differentiated by their role in it: an internal actor is a member of the initiative or, in that case, an associate to it constantly throughout the entire innovation process and that generally has a formal link; an external actor is not formally involved in the initiative, but they know about it and can influence it.

The satisfaction of the internal or external actors of an initiative is key to its sustainability over time. A healthy and communicative relationship between them can improve the results of the initiative and facilitate its dissemination. The satisfaction of an actor is determined by different aspects that are synonymous with trust, both in the initiative and between the different actors. This tool can be used in conjunction with Tool #4, which can provide a deeper understanding of the satisfaction level of the actors.

Target group This tool is designed for initiatives that want to know how the status of the relationship between actors and the initiative is. The tool should be used by initiative coordinators who should manage the survey process, and all relevant actors, internal or external to the initiative, should be involved. The information would be useful for decision making.

This tool is useful during all stages of the initiative, although mostly in the execution stage, where the satisfaction of the actors is crucial for the development of the activities. If updated periodically, the tool can generate information on deviations throughout the initiative, allowing one to detect the evolution of the network and actors relations throughout the initiative.

Materials

- MS Excel file
- Annex 1 - External Actors Survey
- Annex 2 - External Actors Survey.

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

This tool uses data visualization techniques that guide the user's reflection, showing the data in an easy and accessible way. Allows for simple analysis of results, facilitating interpretation and decision making.

What do you need? How to prepare for it?

To use this tool, it is necessary to have access to a computer, tablet, or phone that has the Office package installed. The Excel file is a template for collecting the information obtained through the survey, and at the same time, it has incorporated a visualization system. The first tab is used to enter the information, while the next is created automatically, allowing the data to be viewed. The data collection process must be performed outside of the Excel program, using the annexed format for the survey.

Tool Logic

This tool is made up of two important steps:

Survey Application: using the format in Annex 1 and Annex 2, the user must disseminate the survey to as many actors as possible. It is a quick survey, but it can provide a lot of information on satisfaction. The two available surveys are targeted differently depending on the type of actor: one to external actors, all those actors that are related to the initiative but not part of the managing group; the other is more appropriate to actors actively involved in decision making and deeply involved in the activities. The survey can be carried out anonymously if the initiative considers that the no anonymization would affect the results.

Analysis of Results: The Excel file would be the template for analysing the information obtained. There are two different data entry tables for each of the surveys, identifiable by the tab title. The user will enter the answers in the associated table and the columns dedicated to each actor.

Excel Structure

This tool is made up of three tabs, named: *data entry - external actors*, *data entry - internal actors*, and *dashboard*. The first tab is used to insert the data related to the survey of external actors (Annex 1), while the second is used to insert the data of the survey of internal actors to the initiative (Annex 2). The last tab is a dashboard format that is generated automatically and allows viewing the results in a summarized and general way.

Data Entry

Once positioned in the tab associated with the survey applied, the user will find a matrix where the first column "Item" represents statements about important aspects to monitor the satisfaction of the actors with the initiative, which are also part of the survey in the annexes.

The other columns of the table are dedicated to the systematization of the values obtained by applying the survey to the actors. The coding process of the answers needs to be done following the legend displayed on the upper side of the table.

The tool is designed for 25 actors, if it is necessary to increase the number of actors surveyed, more columns can be created with the excel option 'insert column'.

Illustration 1. Screenshot of the "Data entry - External actors" tab.

EXPECTED RESULTS

Satisfaction survey for external actors

Place the results of the survey according to the following numerical code

Item	Actor 1	Actor 2	Actor 3	Actor 4	Actor 5	Actor 6	Actor 7	Actor 8	Actor 9	Actor 10	Actor 11	Actor 12	Actor 13	Actor 14	Actor 15	Actor 16	Actor 17	Actor 18	Actor 19	Actor 20	Actor 21	Actor 22	Actor 23	Actor 24	Actor 25
The project has known how to satisfy my needs.	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	2	4	4	4	4	3	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Dialogue spaces are sufficient for a correct flow of information	4	3	3	4	1	3	0	4	0	4	0	4	0	1	4	2	0	4	4	4	4	3	2	2	2
How information is transmitted is correct and effective	0	2	2	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	4	1	0	3	3	3	2	2	3	2	2
Feel comfortable giving my opinion when I see fit.	4	4	3	2	3	4	2	2	3	2	2	3	2	3	2	4	2	4	4	3	2	2	4	4	1
The project provided me with information and knowledge that allows me to learn and train	4	1	4	2	4	1	4	2	0	2	4	2	4	1	4	1	4	1	4	2	0	1	2	4	0
know the objectives and goals of the project	1	2	4	1	1	2	4	1	0	1	4	1	4	1	0	1	4	2	4	1	0	2	2	4	0
My interest has remained at least constant since the beginning of the project	4	3	4	1	3	3	4	1	0	1	4	4	4	1	4	1	4	3	4	1	4	3	3	0	4
Feel like I am meeting my personal goals by getting involved in this project	4	2	4	1	3	2	4	1	0	1	4	1	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	1	1	2	1	0
Average	3,1	2,6	3,5	2,3	2,6	2,6	3,1	2,3	0,9	2,3	3,1	2,6	3,1	1,6	3,0	1,4	2,5	2,8	3,8	2,3	2,4	2,6	2,4	2,4	1,5

Illustration 2. Screenshot of the tab "Data entry - External actors" showing the colour code visualization.

Illustration 3. Screenshot of the tab 'Dashboard' showing the visualization of the level graph

Once the values have been inserted into the 'External actors' and 'Internal actors' tabs, the user can analyse the results in two different ways: the colour code in the same data entry tables and/or the level graphs automatically generated in the dashboard tab.

If the results are not displayed automatically, it will be necessary to refresh the data (Select Data > Refresh All)

Level Graph

In the dashboard tab, two-level graphs are displayed. Through that, the general status of the results and averaging values can be seen. The graph uses the same colour code as the previous visualizations.

Colour Code

In the two tabs "External Actors" and "Internal Actors", when the data are inserted, the boxes will change colour depending on the value assigned to each item, showing the results visually. This is so that a detailed or general visualization of all aspects and all actors can be made. The topics are organized in a matrix format, where both actors and variables are interrelated. For a more in-depth analysis, the answers of a particular actor can be visually evaluated by analysing the matrix vertically; to make a general consideration about the variables throughout the actors, the matrix can be analysed horizontally. In this visualization, the results are interpreted according to a colour scale from red to green, where red is the lower value, meaning a negative response from the actor, and green is the higher value, meaning a positive response. The last row represents the average of the answers from the corresponding actors.

